

ASSESSMENT OF THE PROFITABILITY TRENDS OF CASSAVA PRODUCTION ENTERPRISES IN OSUN STATE, NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT

The study was carried out to examine the trends in the profitability of cassava production enterprises between 2008 and 2010 in Osun State, Nigeria. A multi-stage sampling technique was used to randomly select 120 farmers from 60 communities in 6 LGAs in the 3 agricultural zones of the State. Structured interview schedule was used as instrument to collect primary data from respondents on their socio-economic characteristics, cost of production and revenue generated from sales of cassava roots and stem cuttings. Data collected was subjected to descriptive statistics, while profitability was computed using Gross Margin analysis. The result showed that majority (33.3%) of the farmers were between 41-50 years with mean age of 38 years, 56.7 percent were males with 75 percent married, while 43.3 percent had primary education. Majority (43.3%) had household sizes of between 7-9 members and 41.7 percent sourced their funds for production from personal savings. Cassava productions in the study area are profitable but with low gross margins. The Gross Margins for cassava production per hectare for the 3 years (2008-2010) were respectively N151,812, N148,492, and N198,400, with their respective cost benefit ratios as 2.56, 2.43, and 2.70. The 'very severe' constraints to cassava production in the study area are Lack of funds (credit), High transport cost and poor prices for products. The study recommended measures to increase root yield and scale of operation of farmers. To mitigate the constraints, the Government should provide micro credit at low interest rates as well as put in place a buy-back policy that would guarantee price stabilization.

KEYWORDS: Cassava production, costs and returns, gross margin, constraints.

INTRODUCTION

Cassava (*Manihot esculanta*), variously designated as Manioc, Tapioca or Yucca has been acknowledged as one of the most popular staple crops, and its role in Nigeria's food security and poverty alleviation can never be over emphasized. Cassava is an essential part of the diet of more than seventy (70) million Nigerians (FAO 2006). It appears to be a 'food choice' even in the face of alternative food options in urban areas. Close to 40 percent of Nigerians consume cassava more than 4 times in a week (Philips et al 2006). Cassava's starchy roots produce more food energy per unit of land than any other staple crop. The amount of carbohydrates contained in dry cassava roots is higher than maize or any other cereal. It supplies close to 40 percent of calorific requirements of Nigerians (Okigbo 1980). All parts of cassava plant are useful, including the foliage which provide substantial amount of protein, minerals (iron and calcium) and vitamins (A and C) when consumed (Dixon et al 2003).

Nigeria's position as the world's largest producer of cassava is not disputed (IFAD 2010, FMA&RD 2010). Annual production is currently put at over 43 million metric tons from a cropped area of about 4 million hectares and average yield of 12.93 tons per hectare (FOA 2009). However, this increasing trend notwithstanding, Ezedinma et al (2007) noted that cassava production in the country is still dominated by smallholder farmers with mean cassava field area of 0.42 hectare per farmer. One critical variable in the expansion of area cultivated to cassava in Nigeria is the availability of improved processing equipment, which released labour, especially female labour from cassava processing, thus allowing them to plant more cassava (Nweke et al 2002). The wide spread cultivation of cassava according to Okigbo (1980) can also be attributed to its ability to adapt to poor soils, easy propagation by stem cutting, resistance to droughts, and relative high yield even without fertilizer application.

The need for sustained production of cassava derives from the fact that outside being the traditional food of the poor; it has the challenges of meeting the food requirements of ever growing urban elite consumers and that of

industries, animal feed, textiles etc. To achieve this objective, the Federal Government of Nigeria under the Agricultural Transformation Agenda has proposed the cultivation of additional 700,000 hectares of cassava before 2015 (FMA & RD 2011) in order to amongst others create value chains, produce high quality cassava flour (HQCF) as substitute for wheat in composite flour, produce modified starches as replacement for imported corn starch, and the utilization of cassava in the production of fuel ethanol. Cassava production as a means of livelihood for millions of Nigerians has been noted in several works including Achem and Akangbe (2007) and Ayoade and Adeola (2009). The COSCA (1991) noted that cassava production was a profitable venture, but the profit margin depended on the variety planted by the farmer. This was corroborated by Bokanga and Tewe (1998) who also noted that optimal yield in cassava, and hence its profitability depends on application of fertilizers. Nwachukwu et al (2008) noted that cassava production enterprises could be more competitive with farmers attaining yields of over 20 tons per hectare if they can embrace improved agronomic practices, as well as high yielding, pest and disease resistant varieties.

Objectives of the study

The broad objective of the study was to investigate the profitability of cassava production enterprises in Osun State. Specifically, the study was designed to:

- i) describe the socio-economic characteristics of cassava root producers (Farmers) in Osun State;
- ii) examine the trend in profitability of cassava production enterprises in the study area;
- iii) outline the constraints to cassava production in the State.

METHODOLOGY

Study Area

Osun State is located in South Western Nigeria, and has an approximate land mass of 9,251 km². It lies between longitude 04^oE and 05^oS and latitude 05^o58'N and 08^o 07'W. The 2006 National census gave the state a population of 3,423 535. Mean annual temperature varies between 21.1^oC and 31.1^oC, while the rainfall patterned after the tropical type, has mean varying between 1150mm and 1700mm. Osun State has 30 Local Government Areas (LGAs) with its administrative capital at Osogbo. It is predominantly Yoruba speaking. The State has 3 agricultural zones namely; Ife-Ijesha, Iwo and Osogbo. Osun State is noted for production of tree crops mainly cocoa, kola, citrus and oil palm. The arable crops grown mostly as mixed crops include cassava, yam, maize, melon, cocoyam and leafy vegetables.

Sampling Technique/Analytical Technique

A multi-stage sampling technique was adopted for the study. In the first stage, 4 LGAs were randomly selected from each of the 3 agricultural zones. The second stage involved a random selection of 5 communities from each LGA, while in the third stage, 2 cassava farmers were randomly selected from each of the 60 communities; making a total of 120 respondents.

Primary data were collected using structured interview schedule as instrument. Osun State Agricultural Development Project (OSSADEP) provided the sampling frame from the list of registered cassava farmers. The ADP Extension Agents were trained on how to administer the instrument. Data captured in the interview schedule covered socio-economic characteristics of cassava farmers, cost of cassava production per hectare (including land preparation, production inputs, labour etc), and the revenue generated from sales of cassava stems (cuttings) and cassava roots. Eight (8) constraints to cassava processing generated through Focused Group Discussion (FGD) with cassava farmers were identified and captured.. The data collected were subjected to simple descriptive statistics like mean, frequency tabulation and percentages. The profit Margin was calculated using the Brown Model (1979) which states that

$$GM = TR - TVC \text{ where}$$

GM	=	Gross Margin
TR	=	Total Revenue
TVC	=	Total Variable Cost

The constraints to cassava production were rated on a 4-point Likert type scale to determine their severity. It should be noted that most farm lands for cassava production were acquired through family inheritance. Fixed costs of simple farm tools (mainly cutlass and hoe) and their replacements were negligible to the extent that they can be ignored when estimating profitability of small scale enterprises (Olukosi and Erhabor,1988).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 showed that the mean age of respondents was 38 years with most (33.3 percent) within the productive age range of 41-50 years. The table (1) also showed that cassava farming is carried out by both gender, but with majority (56.7percent) as males while 75 percent of them are married. Table 1 further showed that majority (43.3 percent) of the farmers had primary education, with only 5 percent having tertiary education. Farmers with experience of between 11 and 20 years were in majority (51.7 percent), 43.33 percent of the families had household sizes of 7-9 members, while most farmers (41.67 percent) sourced funds for production through personal savings with only 5 percent obtaining loans from commercial banks. Farmers interviewed attributed this to the high interest rates charged by commercial banks, and the stringent conditionality required for accessing bank loans.

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents by Socio-Economic Characteristics

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
N= 120		
Age		
10-20	8	6.67
21-30	26	21.67
31-40	30	25.00
41-50	40	33.33
51-60	16	13.33
\bar{X} = 38 yrs		
Gender		
Male	68	56.67
Female	52	42.33
Marital Status		
Single	14	11.67
Married	90	75.00
Divorced	16	13.33
Education Status		
Non Formal Education	38	31.67
Primary Education	52	43.33
Secondary Education	24	20.00
Tertiary Education	6	5.00
Experince in Production		
1-10	30	25.00
11-20	62	51.66
21-30	20	16.67
31-40	8	6.67
Household Size		
1-3	12	10.00
4-6	40	33.33
7-9	52	43.33
> 9	16	13.34
Source of Funds		
Personal Savings	50	41.67
Money Lenders	16	13.33
Cooperative group/Soc.	46	38.33
Bank Loan	6	5.00
Others	2	1.67

Source: Field Survey Data, 2011

The gross margin analysis of cassava production on 1 hectare of land in the study area for three years (2008 – 2010) is shown in Table 2. Average yield of cassava tubers for the period is 12 tons per hectare with total value of production (Revenue) as N249000, N148492, N198400 respectively for years 2008, 2009 and 2010. This is inclusive of the yield of cassava stems (sold as planting materials) at an average of 70 bundles per hectare for the 3 year period. The respective Gross Margins are N151812, N148492 and N198400, while the Benefit/Cost ratios are 2.56, 2.43 and 2.70. Gross margin analysis for the 3 years shows that cassava farming in the study area is moderately profitable, with the highest profit recorded in 2010 where for every N2 there was a return of N0.70 (70 kobo) on investment followed by 2009 (B\C ratio of 2.56). The seemingly low profitability can be attributed to direct family consumption from the farms, which in most cases are not accounted for in the overall production.

Table 2: Analysis of Profitability Trends (2008-2010)

Variable Cost	Unit	Qty	Unit Price			V a l u e		
			2008	2009	2010	2008	2009	2010
<i>A. Land</i>								
Clearing/prepn	Md	16	650	700	800	10,400	11,200	12,800
Ploughing/ridging	Md	16	650	700	800	10,400	11,200	12,800
						20,800	22,400	25,600
<i>B. Inputs</i>								
Cassava cuttings	Bdls	60	120	130	200	7,200	7,800	12,000
Herbicides	Lits	6	1,300	1,000	1,000	7,800	6,000	6,000
Fertilizer	Bgs	4	2,500	3,000	3,600	10,000	12,000	14,400
						25,000	25,800	32,400
<i>C. Labour/Operations</i>								
Planting	Md	13	650	650	700	8,540	8,540	9,100
Herbicides applicant	Md	4	650	700	700	2,600	2,800	2,800
Fertilizer applicant	Md	6	650	650	650	3,900	3,900	3,900
Supplementary weeding	Md	7	650	700	800	4,550	4,900	5,600
Harvesting	Md	12	700	750	800	8,400	9,000	9,600
Transportation cost	P/up	6	1,200	1,500	1,500	7,200	9,000	9,000
Opportunity cost @20%						16,198	17,268	19,600
<i>D. Total Variable Cost (TVC)</i>						97,188	103,608	117,000
<i>E. Output/Returns</i>								
Cassava tubers	Tns	12	19,700	19,900	25,000	236,400	238,800	300,000
Cassava stems	Bdls	70	180	190	220	12,600	13,300	15,400
Total Revenue						249,000	252,100	315,400
Gross Margin (E-D)						151,812	148,492	198,400
Benefit/Cost Ratio (E/D)						2.56	2.43	2.70

Source: Field Survey Data 2011

Table 3 shows analysis of the severity of constraints to cassava production in the study area using a 4-point Likert-type scale. It was computed by summing the scores (frequency multiplied by magnitude of constraints) and determining the mean (\bar{X}) which were then ranked. Results in table 3 revealed that Lack of credit, High cost of transportation and Poor prices of products fall in the category of "very severe" with respective mean scores of 3.66, 3.59 and 3.51. High cost of labour and Government policy with respective mean scores of 2.83 and 2.67 were in the category of "severe", while Availability of planting materials, Poor extension services and High cost of inputs (chemicals) were considered "not severe" with mean scores of 2.30, 2.25 and 2.18 respectively. The response as regards impact of extension services in Table 3 poses a surprise, as extension: farmer's ratio in Nigeria is noted to be as high as 1: 2,500 (Ilevbaoje, 2004). Perhaps, the farmers may have underestimated the importance of extension in increasing their productivity. A similar surprise was also expressed by the response of the farmers regarding availability of planting materials (cassava cuttings), as most farmers interviewed sourced their cuttings from locally (unimproved). This has negative implications on root yield.

Table 3: Analysis of Constraints to Cassava Production (N=120)

Constraints	4 Very Severe	3 Severe	2 Not Severe	1 Indifferent	Σ	X	Rank	Remark
High cost of labour	40(33.3)	30(25.6)	40(33.3)	10(8.3)	340	2.83	4	Severe
Availability of cutting	20(16.7)	18(15)	60(50)	22(18.3)	276	2.30	6	Not severe
High cost of Inputs (chemicals)	14(11.7)	10(8.3)	80(66.7)	16(13.3)	262	2.18	8	Not severe
High Transportation cost	85(70.8)	23(19.2)	10(8.3)	2(1.7)	431	3.59	2	Very severe
Lack of Credit (Fund)	91(75.9)	20(16.7)	8(6.67)	1(8.83)	441	3.68	1	Very severe
Poor Extension Services	10(8.3)	35(29.2)	50(41.7)	25(20.8)	270	2.25	7	Not severe
Poor Prices for Products	69(57.5)	45(37.5)	4(3.3)	2(1.7)	421	3.51	3	Very severe
Government Policy	20(16.7)	50(41.7)	40(33.3)	10(8.3)	320	2.67	5	Severe

Source: Field Survey data, 2011. Parentheses are in percentages

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Limitless opportunities exist for cassava as a crop for addressing food security and enhancing rural income. There are prospects for high revenue generation and profitability if root yield and productivity are increased, and the scale of operation expanded to meet global competitiveness.

The findings of this study showed that:

- a. Cassava production enterprises in Osun State engaged fairly literate farmers (52%) of both gender;
- b. Cassava farmers operated mostly on small scale, ranging between 1.0 and 1.5 hectares;
- c. Most farmers are in the active productive age bracket of between 40 and 50 years;
- d. Cassava production enterprises are profitable, though the revenue generated and income margins are low;
- e. Cassava production enterprises are faced with some constraints; the 'very severe' ones being lack of credit, high cost of transportation and poor prices of products.

To mitigate the constraints identified in the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Farmers should be encouraged to access micro credit in order to increase their scale of production. The fiscal policy should address high interest rate and reduce complex and stringent conditionalities for accessing loans;
2. Government should boost extension delivery in order to increase uptake and utilization of high yielding varieties of cassava cuttings.

3. Tractors and other farm inputs like agro chemicals and fertilizer should be made available to farmers at affordable prices. For instance, under the present Growth Enhancement Scheme (GES), the Government could bear up to 30 percent subsidy for the critical inputs. In this regard, the government is encouraged to implement to the letter the proposed inputs procurement and distribution arrangement under the cassava transformation agenda;
4. The government should put in place sustainable buy-back policy that will encourage cassava production and price stabilization;
5. Farmers should be encouraged to form themselves into viable Cooperative Groups or Associations in order to facilitate access to farm inputs and micro credit.

REFERENCES

- Achem, B.A. and Akangbe, J.A (2007). Perceived Constraints to Cassava Processing in Kwara State, Nigeria. *Journal of Research in Education and Rural Development (JORED)* 3 (1) 187 - 192
- Ayoade, A.R. and G.R. Adeola (2009). Constraints to Domestic Utilization of Cassava in Osun State, Nigeria. *Ozean Journal of Social Sciences* 2 (2): 11.
- Collaborative Study of Cassava in Africa (COSCA) 1991. IITA. Ibadan.
- Dixon, A.G.O and R. Bradyop (2003). Cassava: From poor Farmer Crop to Pace Setters of African Rural Developments. *Chronica Horticulturae* 43: 33-69.
- Ezedinma, C.I and N. Oti (2007). Socio economic Issues in the Development of Cassava Processing Technologies in Nigeria. *Journal of Sustainable Agriculture and Environment* 3 (1) 118-125
- Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (FMA&RD) 2010. Agricultural Statistics: Cropped Area Yield Survey. 10 (3): 12-15.
- Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (FMA&RD) 2011. Agricultural Transformation Agenda – Key Performance Indicators
- Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of the United Nations (2009). FAOSTAT. <http://faostat.org>.
- Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (2006). FAOSTAT. Statistical Database, Agriculture. Rome Italy.
- Ilevbaoje, E.I (2004) Training and Visit Extension System Flourishes in Nigeria. *Berater Innen News* 1;9
- International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD) 2010. Implementation Completion Report (ICR) for Nigeria's Root and Tuber Expansion Programme (RTEP). Lender's Report Pp.5-6, Rome.
- Nweke, F.T., Spencer, D.S.C and Lynam, K.J (2002), The Cassava Transformation: Africa's Best-kept Secret. Michigan State University Press. East Lansing.
- Okigbo, Bede N. (1980). Nutritional Implications of projects giving high priority to the production of staples of low nutritive quality. The case of cassava in the humid tropics of West Africa. Food and Nutrition Bulletin, United Nations University, Tokyo, 2 (4): 1-10.
- Olukosi, J.O and Erhabor, P.O (1988). Introduction to Farm Management: Principles and Applications. AGITAB Publishers, Zaria, pp77
- Philips, T.P, L. Sanni., and M. Akoroda (2006). A cassava Industrial Revolution in Nigeria, the potential for a New Crop. IFAD and FAO, Rome.

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